

ENHANCING CLASS ENGAGEMENT OF BSBM LEARNERS THROUGH INTERACTIVE-MOTIVATIONAL STRATEGIES IN LESSON DELIVERY USING LEARNING MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

The Bachelor of Science in Business Management (BSBM) program, under the Department of Management Studies envisioned the continuous development in teaching-learning delivery and strategies of faculty specifically in utilization of Learning Management System. The researchers wanted to explore the adaption of interactive-learning strategies in motivational process through Google Workspace. The study utilized mixed research designs in the conduct of the study. The implementation of interactive learning strategies in motivational process promotes the: atmosphere of motivation, excitement among students, promotion of fun environment, increase in class involvement and participation, understanding of concepts, and stimulation of class curiosity and thinking. This action research recommends the following: design and explore motivational interactive strategies that are data friendly, student and faculty friendly and time efficient, and encourage the learners to find an environment that will be conducive for their online session learning.

Keywords: Cavite State University, enhancing class engagement, interactive-learning, Google Workspace, mixed research design, motivation, strategies

INTRODUCTION

The adaption of learning management system (LMS) as an avenue of teaching-learning delivery for flexible learning is vital to the success of higher education institutions. This substantiates the movement of Cavite State University – Cavite College of Arts and Trades towards outcome-based education (OBE) as a forefront strategy in addressing various programs it offers. However existence of making the teaching process more interactive and vibrant for learning to the students becomes challenging in utilization of LMS.

Under the Department of Management Studies, the Bachelor of Science in Business Management (BSBM) program envisioned faculty continuous development in teaching-learning delivery and strategies, specifically in the use of LMS. This manner pushes the desire of the researchers to explore the different tools available in LMS in order to increase the students' motivation and engagement as well as their retention of concepts and ideas with the existing intervention and facilitation of the teacher (Abug. et. al., 2021).

Suggested Citation (APA 7th edition):

Mendoza, X.L.D., Abug, N.B., and Tadeo, J.B (2021). Enhancing class engagement of BSBM learners through interactive-motivational strategies in lesson delivery using learning management system. *Asian Intellect Research and Education Journal*, 21(2), 46-52.

Thus, the researchers wanted to explore the adaption of interactive-learning strategies in the motivational process through Google Workspace LMS in order to improve the transfer of knowledge and skills to the students. This action research also serves as a catalyst for the development of the strategies of every faculty member in a higher education institution.

ACTION RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

Generally, this action research aimed to determine the effect of interactive-learning strategies in motivational learning process among BSBM students of Cavite State University – CCAT Campus.

Specifically, the researchers aimed to:

1. design and implement interactive learning strategies in motivational process using LMS;
2. evaluate the implemented interactive learning strategies in motivational process using LMS in terms of;
 - a. class atmosphere of motivation;
 - b. excitement among students /fun environment towards learning;
 - c. class involvement and participation;
 - d. clear understanding of the students toward concepts;
 - e. class comfortability of interaction;
 - f. attention of students; and
 - g. stimulation of class curiosity and thinking;
3. identify challenges in the implementation of interactive-based motivational strategies using LMS; and
4. craft possible action plan to address the challenges encountered in the conduct of learning intervention.

LITERATURE REVIEW

An increasing number of educational institutions across the world have integrated learning management systems into their educational systems. According to Araújo Júnior and Marquesi (2009), a learning management system, or commonly referred to as an LMS, may be defined, from the user perspective, as a virtual environment that aims to replicate face-to-face learning environments with the use of information technology. In a LMS, the interaction happens through devices that modify communication either synchronously or asynchronously, allowing the crea-

tion of various methods to encourage dialogue and the active participation of students (Oliveira, 2016). However, El Bahsha and Daoudb, (2016) noticed that, although some learning management systems provide several functionalities that are crucial to supporting interactive and effective learning, they are not effectively utilized and are mainly used as an online repository to access course materials. In addition, Li and Tsai (2017) claim that accessing learning materials, that is, lecture slides, video lectures, shared assignments, and forum messages, is the most frequently performed online learning activity. Students with completely different functions, motivations, and preferences could exhibit different behaviors once accessing these materials. The researchers suggest utilizing the benefits of digital learning to develop practicable teaching strategies for effectiveness in teaching. Teachers matched with the utilization of their smart teaching strategies play an important role in extending online interactive learning among students (Lin, Chen, and Liu, 2017).

Interactive-learning enabled environments can massively promote learning behavior data and its support of learning behavior. Learning behaviors were divided into different training sets and testing sets. After the interventions of two semesters of interactive-learning behavior, they found that the students' feature recognition and relationship analysis, learners' interest, assessment pass rate, or excellence rate had improved significantly (Xia, 2020). This is also true in the study conducted by Conte and Serratos (2020), who presented an online and interactive design in lieu of understanding and learning cost functions in their respective classes. Graphs and figures were introduced to the observed bi-algorithm following a sequential order from which a coefficient is calculated, and a strategy is therefore proposed which requires a node-to-node mapping, which in turn contributes to the learning process. The learners were allowed to freely critique and identify errors and were subjected to deliberation on what the appropriate cost functions were that would be used as a business model (interactive). This is the first active and interactive learning method applied to graph matching in cost functions and calculations. These properties made the authors' method very useful as far as the learners were concerned. Thus, allowing human interactions into the teaching method would tend to increase the learning potential of the learners. Considerably, Farashahi and Tajeddin (2018) used a sample of 194 undergraduate and graduate students to assess the perceived effectiveness of simulation,

case study, and lecture for developing students' problem-solving skills, interpersonal skills, and self-awareness. Findings indicated that students perceived simulation first, followed by case study and lecture, respectively, as the most effective teaching pedagogy for developing their interpersonal skills and self-awareness. Simulation and case studies, on the other hand, are perceived to be more effective than lectures with regard to problem-solving skills.

At the University of Alicante (Spain), Mora et al. (2020) conducted a collaborative working model. The model was implemented through a learning web-platform with the purpose of enhancing the learning processes of students. Selected students from computer science engineering were encouraged to peer review their classmates' works, make comments, suggest improvements, and assess final assignments while the whole process was being managed and supervised by the teaching staff. Results concealed deeper content assimilation and increased learning in students' several scientific skills. Researchers regard that collaborating in peer assessment enhances the students' motivation and promotes active learning. In addition, researchers claimed that the method could be very helpful and time-saving for instructors, especially in the management of large groups of students. The result of the previous study is also aligned with the study conducted by Abu-Bajeh and Abbas (2021), explained that with the current online education methods depicting asynchronous online education and mixed education, there is a need for an online interactive educational model with good educational performance that activates participation, interaction, and feedback achievement. The researchers also construed that with the current asynchronous online learning methods, this would not be accurate without the role of the teacher or any interaction. In line with this, Cao (2020) explained that time and space are no longer the barriers to learning, which gives the reason and mechanism for why and how LMS has become the key factor in achieving success in higher education. Student interactions in e-learning platforms are text-based, communication and feedback are delayed, resulting in more passive interaction among students, with the majority of them simply completing the tasks assigned by the teacher.

Given that education and learning experiences are dynamic and should address the needs of both industry and academic competence, students' learning experiences should be addressed and developed on a continuous basis. Hence, the study

and research conducted by the mentioned authors provide a pathway to craft and observe interactive-based activities to further enhance the learning experiences of BSBM students at CvSU-CCAT to provide avenues of improvement and a platform of meaningful strategies in the instruction delivery.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study utilized mixed research designs in the conduct of the study. Specifically, this action research used descriptive design to describe the participants' mean scores. Considerably, quasi-experimental approaches were used in the scaffolding of intervention and analyses among the participants. Moreover, inferential and observation designs were utilized to augment and support the findings of the latter design. This action research has a prior null hypothesis that there are no significant differences between the variables under study among classes with motivational-interactive learning strategies and classes without intervention.

Additionally, the authors used likert-scale questionnaires, checklists, and field and observation notes as research instruments as a basis for data analysis. In support of calibrated and standard measures of variables, the researchers have used the motivation-matrix of the University of California Davis, Center for Educational Effectiveness as a key research instrument in this action research. Two classes, each with an average of 35 students, were used by the researchers.

Participants of the Study

The teachers used the two heterogeneous class of BSBM for each three lecture-subjects of BSBM program offered in the campus namely E-Commerce, International Marketing, and Advertising. The first class utilized the interactive-learning strategies whilst the other class did not. In addition, three faculty members were sourced for the teachers responses in this action research.

Adoption and Implementation Process

The authors, through their collective and collaborative ideas to understand and explore the facets of the new normal of learning, attempted to explore strategies to enhance the learning experiences of students using the Google Workspace-Learning Management System as a key delivery tool in instruction delivery. This action research

explored the utilization of motivational interactive-learning strategies prior to class discussion to determine its possible implications for students' motivation, engagement, and performance. Hence, providing a suggestive strategy to improve class delivery as far as business education is concerned.

Figure 1. Ideation to Evaluation Framework

The authors initially brainstormed various motivational learning strategies that would be utilized in this action research. Moreover, the proponents strategize the delivery of intervention through the determination of appropriate tools that will be used in the study, namely: types of motivational strategy, leveling of topics, class flow, classes to be considered, types of assessment, variables to be considered, research instruments, and timeline of intervention. Considerably, the authors have the following assumptions:

- all classes under study were both heterogeneous;
- internet accessibility are almost the same;
- applied in online session; and
- Google Workspace packages were utilized as LMS.

The faculty members have used interactive picture analysis activity, word association game, and picture without caption activity as interventions in this action research. Considerably, the proponents have used the e-commerce, international marketing, and advertising classes of the Bachelor of Science in Business Management Major in Marketing Management program of Cavite State University-CCAT Campus.

Classes were recorded to aid qualitative observation approaches of teacher observers. Online evaluation sheets and students' assessments were provided and evaluated to augment the quantitative data requirement. Descriptive and inferential

statistics were utilized to provide adequate analysis and empirical observation of the intervention.

FINDINGS AND ACTION RESEARCH NARRATIVE

Intervention Assessment

Table 1. Teachers' Observation

Areas of Observation	With Intervention	Without Intervention
Class atmosphere of motivation	There was a presence of high motivational atmosphere upon the implementation of interactive motivational activity prior to discussion. This was attributed to the active participation of students through the provision of their insights actively. Motivational atmosphere was present as students volunteered enthusiastically. Students were ready and are observed to be in high spirit to listen and interact.	Motivation was present but was limited to the question-answer response of some of the students towards the class queries. Limited number of students responded to the class discussion.
Excitement among students / Fun environment towards learning / Class involvement and participation.	Many students answered with strong intention to learn the main discussion after the interactive motivational strategy was utilized. Students were observed to be volunteering in expressing their ideas, questions and insights toward the subject matter discussed.	Few students plainly responded their readiness towards the opening of topic in class discussion.
Clear understanding of the students toward concepts	The students clearly answered the questions. Students can clearly explain the concepts, ideas, and relevant terminologies during class.	There were dominant presence of teachers reiteration of questions and ideas to the students. It was also observed that teachers tend to use alternative form of questions to address particular concepts or ideas.
Class comfortability of interaction	Students were observed to be comfortable in interacting with the class through the presence of fluidly relaying information, asking questions, provision of insights and relating to their own understanding throughout class discussion.	There was dead air observed during class interaction. The teacher tend to call students multiple times and students answered through uncertain response.
Attention of students / Stimulation of class curiosity and thinking	Majority of the students were attentive all throughout the class discussion.	There was dead air observed during class interaction. The teacher tend to call students multiple times.

Table 1 shows the teachers' observation across BSBM students with induced intervention and placebo classes. It generally shows that there were positive results of observed responses from the students such as the willingness of the students in class participation and engagement, confidence in sharing their ideas, and observed attentiveness to queries.

Table 2. Students' Response

Variables	With Intervention		Without Intervention	
	Mean Value	Descriptive Value	Mean Value	Descriptive Value
I felt I am motivated in class	4.28	Highly Agree	3.90	Agree
I felt excited in learning more about the subject matter	4.35	Highly Agree	4.00	Agree
It felt fun and the mood was set for learning	4.14	Agree	3.75	Agree
It is very understandable and concepts were clear	4.31	Highly Agree	4.00	Agree
I participated well in the activity prior to our class discussion	4.05	Agree	3.91	Agree
I am comfortable in interacting in our class	4.05	Agree	3.79	Agree
I paid attention to what is going on in our class	4.20	Highly Agree	3.85	Agree
I found this activity intellectually stimulating	4.23	Highly Agree	3.84	Agree

Table 2 reveals the students' response towards their experiences in their respective classes both from classes that have intervention and without intervention of interactive motivational strategy. Generally, the students were motivated and participated more in classes with intervention as revealed by higher mean values compared to classes without intervention.

Table 3. Significant Difference of Students' Response (With Intervention and Without Intervention)

Variables	Coefficient	p-value	Significance
I felt I am motivated in class	3.3258	0.001	Significant
I felt excited in learning more about the subject matter	3.0930	0.002	Significant
It felt fun and the mood was set for learning	3.4341	0.001	Significant
It is very understandable and concepts were clear	2.5412	0.012	Significant
I participated well in the activity prior to our class discussion	1.1496	0.252	Insignificant
I am comfortable in interacting in our class	1.8797	0.062	Insignificant
I paid attention to what is going on in our class	2.9905	0.003	Significant
I found this activity intellectually stimulating	3.1611	0.002	Significant

Table 3 presents the significant difference of students' response from classes with and without intervention. Most of the variables under study are significant, thus the intervention conducted by the proponents have a conclusive basis that the mean values are higher compared to classes without intervention. Thereby, rejecting the null hypotheses of all variables that has significant interpretation. However, students participation prior to class discussion and being comfortable in class interaction are insignificant. This can be attributed to internet connectivity issues, learning environment factors, and prior moods of students in their classes. Thereby, accepting the null hypotheses of these two variables.

Figure 2. Assessment Scores of Students

Figure 2 shows the assessment scores of students at the end of the class session. Generally, students from classes with intervention performed well in formative assessment scores compared to students from classes without intervention.

Table 4. Teachers' Observation: Challenges

There is a standing challenge of a reliable internet connection.
There is an identified constraint towards gadget compatibility among students.
Some of the students have unconducive space for online learning using the learning management system.
The one hour prescribed online session is not enough to maximize the potential of providing interactive motivational activity.
Collaboration among students were limited due to the absence of physical interaction.

Table 4 shows the challenges that were observe by the teachers. The finding shows that the a priori challenge was the reliability of the internet connection as also revealed by the study conducted by Abug et. al. (2021). Followed by the familiarity towards platform, gadgets and devices.

CONCLUSION

The authors have adopted and utilized the interactive learning strategies in motivation process among BSBM students of Cavite State University - CCAT Campus, the authors conclude that:

1. The selected faculty members of the Department of Management Studies crafted, strategized and implemented an intervention to adopt interactive learning strategies in motivation process of BSBM students using G-suite LMS.
2. The implementation of interactive learning strategies in motivational process promotes the: atmosphere of motivation, excitement among students, promotion of fun environment, increase in class involvement and participation, understanding of concepts, and stimulation of class curiosity and thinking.
3. The faculty researchers have identified the following key challenges:
 - There is a standing challenge of a reliable internet connection.
 - There is an identified constraint towards gadget compatibility among students.
 - Some of the students have uncondusive space for online learning using the learning management system.
 - The one hour prescribed online session is not enough to maximize the potential of providing interactive motivational activity.
 - Collaboration among students were limited due to the absence of physical interaction.

RECOMMENDATION

The researchers recommend the following:

1. design and explore motivational interactive strategies that are data friendly, student and faculty friendly and time efficient;
2. encourage the learners to find an environment that will be conducive for their online session learning;
3. faculty members are encourage to have a prior knowledge towards the compatibility of electronic devices that the students used in online learning; and
4. undertake future action researches concerning the efficiency and efficacy of this type of intervention and other variables that might influence the learning experiences of business students for further understanding and improvement of strategies.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The researchers would like to thank the CVSU-CCAT Administration, particularly the Research and Extension Unit, for their unwavering support of these research endeavors. This scholarly work would also be impossible to complete without the assistance of the researchers' families. The researchers would also like to express their gratitude to the BSBM students who participated in this study. Most importantly, the researchers offer this to the ALMIGHTY CREATOR, who is the source of everything.

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